

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SOCIAL PROTECTION SYSTEM FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES IN UZBEKISTAN: HISTORICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the formation and development of the social protection system for persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan in 1991–2026, according to the current legislative terminology. The study used regulatory legal documents in the field, analytical reports of the United Nations, the World Bank, the World Health Organization, UNICEF, and the UNDP as sources. The development of the social protection policy for persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan was divided into five main stages: the creation of national legal frameworks in 1991–2007; the expansion of social protection guarantees in 2008–2016; the transition to a human rights-based model in 2017–2020; the implementation of international standards in the national system in 2021–2022; the processes of institutional centralization, digitalization, and the introduction of an individual approach to social services in 2023–2026. The study found that the social protection system in Uzbekistan has evolved from a medical-compensatory model to a rights-based and inclusive model, but some systemic problems remain in employment, accessible environment, inclusive education, disability assessment, and the quality of services at the local level.

Key words: persons with disabilities, persons with disabilities, social protection, social services, inclusion, rehabilitation, employment, accessible environment, human rights, Inson Social Services Center, historical periodization.

Introduction

Ensuring social protection of persons with disabilities is one of the priority and integral directions of social state policy. The content of state policy in this area is not limited to the appointment of pensions, benefits and other types of material assistance. The social protection system also provides for the creation of necessary conditions for persons with disabilities to receive education, engage in labor activities, use qualified medical services, move freely, receive necessary information, as well as participate equally in the political, social and cultural life of society. In this regard, this system is manifested as a complex institutional mechanism aimed at satisfying the needs of a person for social security, as well as the practical implementation of his fundamental rights and freedoms. The World Report on Disability, prepared jointly by the World Health Organization and the

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World Bank, notes that more than one billion people worldwide live with some form of disability and face various obstacles to their full participation in health, education, employment, and society [21; p.5]. The report interprets disability not as a condition determined solely by a person's health or medical diagnosis, but as a complex social phenomenon resulting from the interaction between the individual characteristics of a person and the physical, institutional, and social environment that surrounds him. This approach has served to develop conceptual views based on the identification and elimination of existing social and infrastructural barriers, abandoning the assessment of disability solely within the framework of the medical model. After Uzbekistan gained its independence, the formation of a national system of social protection for persons with disabilities has become an objective necessity. The system inherited from the former Soviet Union was mainly based on the principles of establishing a medical diagnosis, determining the degree of incapacity for work, assigning pensions and benefits, and providing social services in stationary institutions. This approach did not sufficiently take into account the legal status of persons with disabilities, ensuring their independent life and active participation in society. During the years of independence, the legal, institutional and social foundations of this system were gradually improved. As a result of the changes implemented, a process of transition began from considering a person with disabilities only as an object receiving state assistance and social security measures to an approach based on recognizing their independent rights as owners of rights. Thus, the necessary conceptual foundations were created for the formation of a legal model aimed at ensuring the human dignity of persons with disabilities in social protection policy, creating equal opportunities, preventing discrimination and supporting their full integration into society.

Research methodology

The principles of historicity, objectivity, systematicity, and comparative analysis were consistently followed in the implementation of the research. These principles made it possible to study the formation and development of the social protection system for persons with disabilities in an inextricable link with specific historical conditions, socio-political processes, and legal and institutional changes. Based on the historical-genetic method, the factors of the emergence of the social protection system, its initial organizational and legal foundations, and the processes of its gradual improvement in subsequent periods were analyzed. This method served as an important methodological tool in determining the internal laws, duration, and cause-and-effect relationships of changes in social

protection policy. Using the historical-comparative method, the content, priority areas, and conceptual approaches of the laws adopted in 1991, 2008, and 2020 were compared. In the process of comparative analysis, special attention was paid to the evolution of norms regarding the legal status of persons with disabilities, social protection measures guaranteed by the state, mechanisms for ensuring equal opportunities, and full participation in the life of society in these laws. This made it possible to identify the general and specific aspects of legal approaches that were in force in different periods, as well as the tendency to transition from a social security model to a model based on human rights. Institutional analysis was used to study the powers, functions, and mechanisms of interaction of state administration bodies, local government bodies, the medical and social expertise system, "Human" social service centers, and civil society institutions in this area. Through this approach, the organizational structure, functional tasks, and place of institutions implementing the policy of social protection of persons with disabilities in the service delivery system were analyzed. At the same time, the impact of institutional reforms on the targeting, effectiveness, and responsiveness of social services to the needs of citizens was assessed. The content analysis method was used in the study of regulatory legal documents. During the analysis, the features of application, substantive interpretation and expression in legal norms of the concepts of "social assistance", "right", "equal opportunities", "non-discrimination", "inclusion", "individual approach" and "barrier-free environment" in legislative documents were systematically studied. The role and content of these concepts in regulatory legal documents adopted in different periods were used as a criterion for determining changes in the conceptual foundations of social protection policy. In order to strengthen the empirical and information base of the study, statistical indicators and expert opinions in reports published by the UN, UNICEF, the World Bank and the UNDP were critically analyzed. This information was compared with materials on national legislation and institutional practice, and their reliability, methodological foundations and scientific significance in covering the research topic were assessed. As a result, a methodological approach was developed that allows for a comprehensive analysis of the legal, historical, and institutional processes of the development of the social protection system for persons with disabilities.

Literature review

Scientific and analytical studies aimed at studying the social situation of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan mainly cover issues related to the regulatory and legal framework for ensuring their rights, educational

opportunities, employment, medical and social rehabilitation, and access to social services. Although these studies have generated important scientific conclusions on specific areas of the social protection system for persons with disabilities, most of the existing literature does not provide a comprehensive analysis of the emergence, stages of development, and conceptual changes of this system as a single historical process. A situation analysis prepared in 2019 with the participation of UN agencies showed that the approach to disability in Uzbekistan is a mixed one, combining elements of medical, charitable, and social models. The authors of the report note that in practice, a person with a disability is often interpreted not as an independent right holder and an equal subject of social relations, but as a recipient of assistance in need of state and social support [9; B.46]. This conclusion indicates that in the country's social protection system, some elements of the traditional medical-charitable model and a rights-based approach are preserved in parallel. The "Analysis of the Situation on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in Uzbekistan", published in 2021, noted that the number of initiatives aimed at improving legislation and updating state policy in this area in the period after 2018 has significantly increased compared to the initiatives implemented over the previous twenty years. At the same time, the study revealed certain discrepancies between the guarantees established in regulatory legal acts and their practical implementation at the regional and local levels [10; p.65]. This situation indicates the need to assess reforms in the field not only on the basis of changes in legislation, but also from the point of view of their implementation in institutional practice and the real impact on the daily lives of persons with disabilities. The World Bank's country profile for Uzbekistan assessed the reforms initiated in 2017, the adoption of a new law in 2020, and the ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 2021 as key turning points in the development of national policies on social protection for persons with disabilities [11; p.16]. These processes have created an important legal and institutional basis for the transition of social protection from traditional mechanisms of provision and compensation to a model based on the principles of human rights, equal opportunities, non-discrimination, and social inclusion. Unlike existing scientific and analytical works, this article studies the system of social protection of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan as a holistic historical process from the early period of state independence to 2026. The development of the system is studied on the basis of historical periodization, and the normative, legal, institutional and conceptual changes inherent in each stage are analyzed in their interrelation. Such an approach allows us to identify the regularities of the

formation of the social protection system, the continuity and discontinuities in its development, as well as the process of transition from a support-based model to an approach that recognizes the legal entity of a person with disabilities.

Results and discussions

The initial legal foundation of the national system of social protection of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan was created on November 18, 1991 with the adoption of Law No. 422-XII “On Social Protection of Persons with Disabilities in the Republic of Uzbekistan”. This document, which entered into force on January 14, 1992, was one of the main laws regulating the sector in the early period of independence and made it possible to regulate relations related to social protection within the framework of national legislation [1; Articles 1–6]. The historical significance of the law was manifested when social protection of persons with disabilities was recognized as an independent direction of state policy. It established the legal basis for medical care, rehabilitation, education, vocational training and employment guarantees, the obligations of state bodies and organizations, pensions, social assistance and other benefits. As a result, previously dispersed protective measures were systematized within a single sectoral law. However, on the conceptual basis of the law, disability was interpreted, first of all, as physical or mental disorders in the human body and limitations in work capacity. Social protection was understood as a system of compensation for these limitations through material, medical and organizational measures. Although this approach formed important social guarantees, it did not sufficiently take into account the social, institutional and environmental factors of disability. In the 1990s, changes in the economic system, reorganization of enterprises and restrictions on state financial capabilities had a negative impact on the employment of persons with disabilities. In the context of the weakening of specialized enterprises and mechanisms for guaranteed jobs, pensions, benefits, medical examinations, prosthetic and orthopedic devices, and services in boarding schools remained a priority. Therefore, the years 1991–2007 can be characterized as the “compensatory-institutional stage” of social protection. At the same time, the 1991 law established the rights to education, work, and access to infrastructure, creating the initial regulatory conditions for the subsequent transition to a human rights-based model. The next stage in the development of the social protection system began on July 11, 2008, with the approval of a new version of the Law “On Social Protection of Persons with Disabilities in the Republic of Uzbekistan” by Law No. 162. This document, consisting of 36 articles, systematized the previous norms and expanded the main areas of social

protection [2; Articles 1–6]. The law defined social protection of persons with disabilities as a system of economic, social, and legal measures guaranteed by the state, aimed at eliminating or compensating for limitations in life activities and creating the opportunity to participate in society on an equal basis with other citizens [2; Article 3]. The new version separately regulates the following areas: 1. Unhindered access to social infrastructure, transport, communications, and information. 2. Medical, social, psychological, pedagogical and vocational rehabilitation. 3. Preschool, general secondary, vocational and higher education. 4. Employment and the organization of special jobs. 5. Social and household services and material assistance. 6. Activities of public associations of persons with disabilities.

These norms served to link social protection not only with material support, but also with education, employment, access to infrastructure and participation in public life. However, the use of concepts such as “impairment”, “restricted life activity” and “person in need of social assistance” indicates the preservation of a medical-compensatory approach. The adoption of Law No.-415 “On Social Services for the Elderly, Persons with Disabilities and Other Socially Needy Categories of the Population” on December 26, 2016 was an important institutional innovation. It regulated the issues of identifying persons in need of social services, types of services, powers of state bodies and the development of individual service programs [3; Articles 1–7]. This law created the legal basis for the transition from a system based on cash payments and stationary institutions to a model of services that takes into account the life situation, health, family environment and individual needs of the person. However, the distribution of powers between different agencies has limited the ability to coordinate services, maintain a single record, and assess effectiveness. A 2019 UNICEF analysis noted that, despite the legal reforms implemented, serious obstacles to the realization of the rights of children and adults with disabilities remain, and that some practices contain elements of segregation and a charitable model [9; p.16]. Thus, although the years 2008–2016 were characterized by the expansion of social guarantees, the individual’s medical condition and need for state assistance remained at the center of the system. The conceptual renewal of disability policy in Uzbekistan has reached a new stage since 2017. Presidential Decree No. PD-5270 of December 1, 2017, set out the tasks of implementing the requirements of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities into national legislation, developing a new draft law, creating a barrier-free environment, and expanding educational and employment opportunities [4; paragraphs 1–3]. The program

attached to the decree provided for replacing the term “disabled” with the concept of “person with a disability” [4; p.4]. This terminological change was a conceptual shift aimed at abandoning the identification of a person with his or her disability status and recognizing him or her, first of all, as a human being, a citizen, and an independent holder of rights. As part of the 2017 reforms, a mechanism was introduced for admitting persons with disabilities to higher education institutions on the basis of additional state grant quotas [4; paragraph 9]. This served to assess education not as a form of social assistance, but as a right that ensures the professional development and economic independence of an individual. The Presidential Decree No. PD-4860 of October 13, 2020 approved the Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System for 2020–2025 [5; paragraph 1]. It provided for the involvement of children with special educational needs in general education schools, the training of teachers, the adaptation of infrastructure, and the development of special methodological support. The UNICEF analysis also noted that the transition from special educational institutions to inclusive education has begun, but there is a need to change school infrastructure, pedagogical training, and stereotypes in society [13; p.1]. An important result of the reforms was the adoption of Law No. 641 "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" on October 15, 2020. The law, which entered into force on January 16, 2021, replaced the 2008 document and regulated the legal status of persons with disabilities on a new conceptual basis.

The law enshrines the principles of respect for the dignity and worth of the individual, independence, non-discrimination, equality of opportunity, full participation in the life of society and the state, access to facilities and services, and respect for the evolving capacities of children with disabilities [6; Article 4]. Disability is defined as a condition resulting from the interaction of a person with a persistent physical, mental, sensory or psychological impairment and environmental factors that hinder their full participation in society [6; Article 3]. Thus, the transition from a medical model to a social and human rights-based model has been enshrined at the legislative level. Article 6 of the law prohibits discrimination on the basis of disability, Article 9 establishes the openness of state bodies, and Article 18 establishes access to facilities and services [6; Articles 6, 9 and 18]. However, the implementation of these norms in the practice of construction, transport, information, education, employment and local governance required long-term institutional changes. Uzbekistan ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which it signed in 2009, by Law No. 695 of June 7, 2021 [7; Article 1]. The Convention requires states to

eliminate discrimination, ensure reasonable accommodation, independent living, inclusive education, health care, rehabilitation, employment, and participation in political and public life [8; Articles 4, 9, 19, 24, 27 and 29]. As a result of ratification, firstly, ensuring the rights of persons with disabilities has become an international legal obligation. Secondly, there is a need to align national legislation and state programs with the principles of the Convention. Third, the involvement of persons with disabilities and their organizations in decision-making processes has been strengthened. Fourth, the need to assess the effectiveness of public policies not by the amount of benefits and expenditures, but by the independent life and social participation of individuals has increased. The 2021 situation analysis showed that, despite the acceleration of legal reforms, physical barriers, restrictions on access to information, a lack of inclusive services, and stereotypes persist [10; p.65–67]. According to UNICEF analysis, approximately 52 percent of children with severe disabilities are covered by appropriate benefits, while the rest are affected by diagnostic, registration, and administrative barriers to their use [12; p.17]. Therefore, 2021–2022 can be considered as an initial stage in the recognition of international standards and their implementation in national policies. Although the legal framework has been strengthened, the lack of a state body coordinating services on the basis of a single policy has limited the effectiveness of the system. By Presidential Decree No. PD-82 of June 1, 2023, the National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and “Inson” social service centers in districts and cities were established [14; paragraphs 1–5]. The decree stipulated the organization of services at the mahalla level, individual assessment of the needs of the individual and family, the establishment of professional social workers, and the coordination of services at a single point [14; paragraph 2].

The “Human” centers were tasked with assessing needs, forming a social passport, drawing up an individual service plan, organizing services through state and non-state organizations, monitoring results, and applying the case management method in complex situations [14; paragraphs 5–6]. This system represented a transition from a departmentally dispersed model of social protection to a model of integrated, person-oriented services. Resolution No. PD-74 of February 27, 2023 established measures to organize the provision of prosthetic and orthopedic devices and rehabilitation equipment through an electronic platform, create transparent queues, and support students with disabilities [15; paragraphs 1–12]. Presidential Resolution No. PD-257 of July 16, 2024 provided for improving the process of determining disability, electronic

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transmission of medical documents, and the introduction of mechanisms based on assessing a person's daily activity and social participation [17; 1–4]. This represents a shift from an assessment based on medical diagnosis to one that takes into account functional capabilities and environmental factors. The effectiveness of the new system depends on the transparency of the criteria, the training of specialists, complaint mechanisms and the consideration of the individual's opinion. Employment of persons with disabilities remains one of the most complex areas of social protection. The 2019 analysis noted that the employment rate of persons with disabilities was 7.1 percent, compared with about 30 percent among the general population [9; p.147].

According to the 2024 report, there were about 845.3 thousand disability certificates in Uzbekistan, which was about 2.3 percent of the population. Of the 162.2 thousand people assessed as able-bodied, only 21.1 thousand were officially employed [16; p.8–9]. These figures indicate that official statistics do not fully reflect the real scale and that a large part of people with work potential remain outside the open labor market. Presidential Decree No. PD-85 of May 8, 2025 established subsidized reimbursement of the costs of entrepreneurs who hire people with disabilities of groups I and II and organize a sign language interpreter, psychologist or escort service for them [19; paragraphs 1–5]. This mechanism encourages the employer to create the necessary “reasonable accommodation” conditions for them, not only by hiring a person. It is necessary to develop harmoniously the mechanisms of vocational training, retraining, supported employment, remote work, social entrepreneurship and job adaptation, not limiting the employment policy to quotas. In accordance with Decree No. PD-258 of December 26, 2025, the goal of ensuring official employment of 40 thousand people with disabilities through the “Equal Opportunity — Inclusive Employment” program in 2026 was set [20; paragraphs 1 and 9–10]. For a long time, stationary and specialized institutions have been the priority in providing services to children with disabilities. Presidential Decree No. PD-41 of February 3, 2025 established the phased introduction of day care services based on public-private partnership for children with disabilities aged 3 to 18 [18; paragraphs 1–4]. This service allows the child to use developmental, rehabilitation and social services without separating from his family, and allows his parents to continue their work. This is an important aspect of the transition from a stationary model to a system of family and community-based services. As a result of historical development in 1991–2026, an independent national legislative system for social protection of persons with disabilities was formed in

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Uzbekistan. Legal regulation expanded from material assistance, pensions and medical services to ensuring non-discrimination, equal opportunities, a barrier-free environment, independent living and full participation in society. There was a conceptual transition in state policy from a compensation model to a human rights-based approach. The ratification of the Convention brought national policy into line with international standards. Inclusive education, employment in an open labor market, the right to access information and infrastructure became independent policy directions. The National Agency for Social Protection and the Human Centers have established an institutional framework for coordinating services, identifying individual needs, and implementing case management. Mechanisms for involving the non-governmental and private sectors in rehabilitation, day care, and employment services have also begun to develop.

However, legal guarantees for creating a barrier-free environment are not fully provided in all facilities. The presence of a ramp does not mean that the building is accessible to everyone; the entrance, doors, elevator, sanitary facilities, information signs, voice messages and service procedures must comply with universal design requirements. Despite the introduction of functional assessment, in practice, medical diagnosis may remain the main criterion. The assessment should comprehensively take into account the barriers in the person's daily life, education, work, mobility, communication and environment. Problems in employment are not only associated with a lack of vacancies. The mismatch of vocational training with the requirements of the labor market, stereotypes among employers, inadequate transport and workplaces, and a lack of accompanying services are also important factors. The distribution of rehabilitation, diagnostic, psychological, speech therapy and vocational services by region is uneven. When assessing the activities of the "Human" centers, the number of services, as well as their quality, duration, compliance with individual needs and the impact on the life of the individual, should be taken into account. Inclusive education is not limited to enrolling a child in a general education school. It is necessary to adapt school buildings, train special educators, psychologists and assistants, create textbooks in Braille, large print, audio and simplified formats. Only persons with a disability status are included in official statistics. Persons who have not undergone an examination, have not issued a document or do not use services may be excluded from the calculation. This makes it difficult to identify real needs, plan services and allocate budget funds. When developing a policy on the rights of persons with disabilities, it is necessary to adhere to the principle "Nothing about us without us". Their participation and that of public organizations should

not be limited to discussing ready-made documents, but should also cover the stages of identifying the problem, developing solutions, designing, implementing services, monitoring and evaluating results. In general, the system of social protection of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan has evolved from a compensatory model of state assistance to a system based on human rights, individual needs and social participation. However, the full implementation of this model depends on the consistent implementation of legal norms at the level of regions, neighborhoods, educational institutions, workplaces and public services. The main criterion for the effectiveness of the system should not be the number of benefits or services provided, but rather the practical provision of the opportunity for a person with disabilities to live independently, receive quality education, work decently and participate in society on an equal basis with others.

Conclusion

The system of social protection of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan has undergone a complex and multi-stage historical evolution during the years of state independence. Taking into account the normative-legal, institutional and conceptual features of this process, its development can be divided into five interrelated historical stages. The first stage — “1991–2007” — is the period when independent national legal frameworks for social protection of persons with disabilities were formed. At this stage, the state policy was dominated by a medical-compensatory and institutional protection model aimed at assessing disability mainly in terms of medical condition and limitations in work capacity, and compensating for existing limitations through pensions, benefits, medical care, rehabilitation and inpatient services. The second stage — “2008–2016” — is characterized by the expansion of legal guarantees for social protection. During this period, the regulatory and legal framework for rehabilitation, education, vocational training, employment, access to infrastructure facilities and the provision of social services was strengthened. At the same time, some legal mechanisms aimed at ensuring the participation of persons with disabilities in society, not limiting social protection to material assistance and inpatient services, began to form. However, at this stage, the medical-compensatory approach did not completely lose its leading position. The third stage — “2017–2020” — is the period when the transition to a human rights-based approach in state policy, legal terminology and legislation began. The tendency to recognize a person with disabilities not as a passive object of state assistance and patronage, but as an independent right holder and an equal subject of social relations has increased. The transition from the term “disabled person” to the concept of

“person with a disability”, the consolidation of the principles of barrier-free environment, inclusive education, equal opportunities and non-discrimination in the legislation were the main manifestations of this conceptual change. The fourth stage — “2021–2022” — is characterized by the ratification of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and the acceleration of the process of implementing international standards in the national social protection system. The ratification of the Convention brought the issue of ensuring the rights of persons with disabilities from the framework of the state’s internal social policy to the system of international legal obligations. As a result, the need to align national legislation, state programs and institutional practice with the principles of human dignity, independence, equality, non-discrimination and full participation in society has increased.

The fifth stage — “2023–2026” — is characterized as a period of institutional renewal of the social protection system. The establishment of the National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and territorial “Human” social service centers, the introduction of case management practices, the transition to functional disability assessment mechanisms, the expansion of electronic services, and the formation of new mechanisms aimed at ensuring inclusive employment are the main features of this stage. These changes represent the process of transition from a departmentally dispersed model of services to a system of social services focused on the individual needs of the individual and integrated. The results of historical analysis show that in Uzbekistan there has been a significant conceptual shift from assessing persons with disabilities as objects of state care and material support to recognizing them as independent rights holders, active participants in public life, and equal citizens. This change is reflected in the terminology of legislation, priorities of state policy, principles of organization of social services, and criteria for assessing disability. At the same time, the full implementation of the human rights-based model is not determined only by the adoption of regulatory legal acts. The practical effectiveness of this model depends on the consistent and uniform implementation of the rights and guarantees established by the legislation in each region, neighborhood, educational institution, medical organization, transport facility, workplace, and public service. The transformation of legal norms into real opportunities in everyday life requires adapting infrastructure based on universal design, ensuring territorial equality of services, developing mechanisms for inclusive education and employment, as well as directly involving persons with disabilities in decision-making processes. The amount of benefits assigned,

benefits provided, or services provided cannot be the only and main criterion for assessing the effectiveness of the modern social protection system being formed in Uzbekistan. The primary criterion for the effectiveness of the system should be the level of practical provision of the opportunity for a person with a disability to live independently, receive quality education, engage in decent work, freely use necessary services, and participate in the life of society and the state on an equal basis with other citizens.

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